

Impact of A.V Aids on Academic Achievement of Students at Secondary School Level in Southern Districts of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan

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Abstract

AV aids are very important in the learning process. It prepares students for useful learning. There is no doubt that learning materials have great importance in education. Due to this the researcher conducts a study regarding “impact of AV AIDS on the academic achievement of students”. A descriptive nature study was conducted. All the 10th class students of Gov secondary schools were the study population. As a sample 500 respondents were selected from 12 Govt. secondary schools, by applying a simple random sampling technique. The researcher delimited the study only to 10th grade of the 12 females and males’ schools. To collect the data, a self-made tool was used. The collected data was analyzed by SPSS. John Curry formula was applied. Frequency, percentage, and linear regression were used for analysis. It was revealed that students’ academic achievement has a positive relation with AV aids.

Key Words: Audio Visual aids, Students' academic achievement, and Secondary School.

Introduction

A.V aids are those learning resources that are used in the classrooms by the teachers to improve and promote the teaching-learning process. Using these materials, carry out the educational course in a successful as well as conceptual way. It captures the concentration of the learners easily and make the teachers capable. to describe and put in plain words the concept very easily and interestingly. Further, it was also stated that when the students see and hear the related materials, the topic becomes very easy and understandable, because without seeing and hearing the lesson remain less informative. (Ellingtan, H. 1993).

Materials such as T.V, radios, projectors, film strips, models, maps, and charts were given the name of instructional materials or AV aids. These aids gave practical knowledge to the students and helped them in understanding the history and also capture the student’s attention. According to the famous proverb that “One’s see is worth a hundred words follow”. It is a fact that if we see we keep it in mind but if we only hear and do not see we forgot it, but when we acted we understand (Rasol Bakhesh & Batool, 2011).

Site of the Study

The present study was conducted in twelve districts’ secondary school of Lakki Marwat and Bannu of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. Both districts are situated near FATA (Federally Administrated Tribal Areas) of Pakistan. The total numbers of the students that were boys and girls in Bannu and Lakki Marwat were 11506 and 11656 respectively. KPK District of Educational Management Information System (2015-16).

Review of Related Literature

The devices which are used in the class for promoting all the educational programs and make it effective, interesting and easier is given the name of AV Aids or learning resources (Iqbal, M.2005). A study

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revealed that there was a very distinct difference among those students who were taught using A V aids in the classroom and who left without AVids ; there was much difference in their academic score. Those who were taught in the class with using proper A V aids they secure high marks in the annual examination instead of those who were delivered the lesson without using these resources (Ellington H. 1993) Using of charts, maps, projector and TV also help the instructors, because they teachers easily come to understand, remember, think and solve the problems related to their students during the teaching-learning process. It means that through audio-visual aids we can easily judge and make a decision (Oladigo MA, ET al2011) stated that using of instructional materials in the class, helped in making the students' concept and concentration as well as improve their perception and cognition. Further, it was also concluded that proper uses of audiovisual aids bring positive changes in the students' behaviors, concepts, and in their perception. (Quraco NR, et al 2012).Providing proper and cheap facilities of the resources for the learners at their institutions plays key roles in the whole system of education. It is also needed to provide a suitable place while using A V aids. Besides this, it is also stated that it must be kept in mind to make available opportunities and a fruitful environment for the standard teaching-learning process. He explained that those teachers are also required to become aware of the proper use of learning resources because, without proper and effective use of these materials, it brings negative changes and waste the precious time of both the teachers as well students. He recommended that if there is no trained teacher and no proper use of these resources, will lead the students to become fed up and their attention will not be got easier and it will make the teaching-learning process flap and boring (Iqbal, M.2005). The world's majority countries that are less developed such as Pakistan, in which instructional materials are not properly used in the educational institutions for the whole instruction periods. They searched out that there are so many reasons which are responsible for the misuse and improper use of these materials. Further, they described that due to the lack of instructional resources, the educational standard is very low, due to which students cannot get and secure high marks, as a result their academic performance is badly affected, especially at the secondary school level. It was also stated that in less developing countries teachers have no proper training regarding the effective use of these aids. Today modern technology like multimedia, projectors, and computers make the overall educational programs easy, interesting, and effective (Sulaiman, Q, et al, 2012).In schools and colleges, A V aids are used as highly effective sources. Further, it was also explained that proper use of the resources enables the students to learn more and more. He explained that improper use of these materials makes the program defective and the students may lose their courage and become demotivated. It was investigated that those students who have used Av aids during their lesson, showed better performance in the form of .academic score, as compare to those. who do not use the resources in the class during their lesson. Presenting of audio-visual aids in a better way can improve understanding and make clear the concept of the lesson, make the lesson interesting and understandable (H.David Breh, 2012).

Factors that are necessary for academic achievement, there are four central factors as well as the sharp insufficiency of learning materials which he thought unnatural education system from responding more completely to innovative stress. He stated that in order to stop the disaster in education, the educational system needs authentic resources, that is possible after increase in the educational funds, they need a complete contribution of the national manpower also not only to take the current labor of education but to lift its quality, effectiveness, and outcomes. He described that they need proper physical facilities like school building and teaching-learning materials etc. (Coombs, P.H.1970).

It is investigated in a study about A.V aids in eight teacher training institutes in Kawara state. Further, he also examined twelve (12) training colleges in Nigeria. He described that learning materials gained by every selected training institute, proper use of these own resources have a positive relationship with student's performance. He stated that in those areas where there was the use of these materials, the achievement of the students was better than those where there was no use of these materials (Akolo J.B. 1978). Human resources have discussed comprehensively by different experts on the significance of the instructors to the learning progress of a state be it trouble-free, urbanized, and complex. According to these experts, one can conclude that whatever facilities are provided, which subject matter is taught, in which surroundings are the college, school or university located and what type of student is taught, the significant and basic position of the facilitator cannot be neglected. Lacking these amenities that are

humans or teachers and material resources, successful learning cannot take place because the teacher's place is very important in the educational system (Fafunwa, B. 1969).

Materials like charts, models, experiments, doing a demonstration during the lesson in the class can improve the knowledge and motivate them. Also, they described the use of instructional resources to make learning easy, interesting, fast, and effective and save the time and energy of both the students and teachers. Proper use of AV aids during classroom instructions can improve learning by leading the individual to be creative-minded (Moeller & Reitzes, 2011). A Whiteboard or blackboard is very important. Teachers should use a whiteboard or blackboard to develop a summary of the lesson (Nzewvihe, 2011). The opinions of the secondary school teachers on the use of the instructional resources projector, animation videos films, and pictures as the most important and motivational tools in gaining students' focus and attention in reading literary texts. They selected both the teachers and students of private and public schools. In this study majority of the respondents were given positive responses about the utilization of the instructional resources in classrooms (Shabira Lyni, et al, 2015).

A survey type research is conducted which aimed to investigate the extent to which the AV aids were used in schools and their impact on teacher teaching and students' learning process in non Govt Secondary Schools. During this study one hundred and twenty respondents took part. The result showed that the use of these resources has a significant impact on the teaching-learning process of secondary school students (Ojowu Ode Elijah, 2014). It is investigated that charts are cheap, useful, and easy to use as A.V. aids, which can help the teachers and students to understand better e.g. different processes, such as flow diagrams, etc. Many effective explanations use charts to make better the understanding of the readers over the important points of a topic. This resource help in gaining the students' attention and make their lesson interesting and make easier the points which are difficult to cover only with the help of theory (Dahar and Faize, 2011).

A study explained to examine the benefits that come from A.V. aids in the form of an increase in the vocabulary of teachers as well as the increase in obtaining English language, knowledge, and concepts about different topics by the learners. With the help of the quantitative method, the data of the study showed the use of AV Aids improves both the instructor and learner language because it allows using different words about different aspects of a topic (Al Mamun Md. Abdullah, 2014). Research stated the benefit of teleconferencing for the classroom that used to get experiences of that concerned person, whose physical presence is difficult due to some reasons for involving in topic with his studio items, classroom students, company colleagues, etc. This use of technological aids makes it easiest for the learners to ask a question from the concerned person with the distance of so many miles (Jadal, 2011).

A study conducted on the proper use of these resources' learning process, is the approach which boosts and improves the lesson and provides the students' extra ways to practices the content information. Further, it was too stated that students took more interest in the education where there were effectively use of the learning resources. The researcher concluded that in this way we can assess the desire and interest of every student. Authors like Shakespeare may be very easy to know when the related materials are seen and read. Films are very helpful in highlighting historical events to provide an analysis of the present situations (J. Naga Madhuri, 2013).

A researcher investigated to examine the impact of AV Aid on the University learners' learning process. Conclusions were drawn from the findings. After findings, the following conclusions were drawn (a) According to the respondents' views AV Aids take a pivotal part in effective schooling situations (b) It was also found that using instructional resources, can make all the education programs very interesting and successful. (c) The respondents' views showed that making use of the resources in the class during the lesson provide very deep and comprehensive knowledge. Further, the researcher recommended that. (1) It is very important for the teachers that they must be very clear and prepared before going to use AV aids in a better and effective way. (2) It was also recommended that the teachers must need to do planning before going to make the use of the learning resources. (3) Audiovisual materials should be according to the needs, stage, and concentration of the student. (4) The researcher recommended that students may also give proper training regarding the use of the available learning aids (Rasul Saima,2011).

From the above studies the researcher distinguishes that Maps, Globes, Charts, Color Charts, Chalk, Pointer Pens of Different Colors, Models, Multimedia, Computers, Projectors Teleconferencing, Film Strip, Radio, Tap Record, etc. have a very significant role in gaining knowledge in the classroom. Subsequently there is no doubt with the idea that these materials have a significant relationship with students' academic achievement. Keeping in view this importance, the investigator decided to carry out a research which is entitled as under;

Problem Entitled

“Impact of audiovisual aids on Student Academic Achievement at Secondary School Level in Southern Districts of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan.

Research Methodology

Research Design

It was a descriptive nature study, for data collection survey method was used for the collection of information from the twelve Govt. secondary schools' students of district Bannu and Lakki Marwat. The researcher developed a self-made questionnaire for the collection of the related data.

The population of the study

All the secondary schools' students of the Govt. Secondary Schools were in Southern Districts of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan were taken as the study population

Sample Size and Sampling Technique

As a sample five hundred female and male students as the respondents of the study were selected from the below six Govt, Secondary Schools as shown in table No: 3.1. From each school, 250 male and female respondents were taken, by using John Curry Sample of size, the researcher has taken the respondents through Simple random Sampling technique.

Table 1. Shows Sample of the total respondents

District Bannu	Respondents	District Lakki Marwat	Respondents
Male secondary schools (03)	125 Boys students	Male secondary schools (03)	125 Boys students
Female secondary schools (03)	125 Girls students	Female secondary schools (03)	125 Girls students
Total numbers of male & female secondary schools (06)	Total numbers of respondents 250	Total numbers of male & female secondary schools (06)	Total numbers of respondents 250

John Curry Formula rule 3of thumb used for the determination of Sample Size

Rule of thumb Sample

10-100	100%
101-1000	10%
1001-5000	5%
5001-10000	3%
10000+	1%

Source: (Curry, J.1984) Professor of Educational Research, North Texas University.

Analysis of Data

The collected data was correctly analyzed by the using Statistical Software Package for social science (SPSS version16). During the analysis of the data linear regression model, Frequency and percentage were used as descriptive statistics.

Measurement Scale

To measure the views of the respondents, the researcher used the Dichotomous scale containing (Yes and No) options, and the value of 1 and 2 were used which is given the table below.

Table 2. Indicates the Design of the Scale

Version	Yes	No
Values	1	2

Pilot study

The pilot study is a very essential part of conducting good research. The aim of the present investigation was to validate the research tools before going to conduct a study. To validate the research tools, the initial draft of the tools was administered among eleven experts. In these seven were educationists, two were a psychologist and two have linguists. . Some corrections which were found by the experts in the tools, conceptions, wording, and phrases, etc were incorporated accordingly. The incorporated and final draft of the research tool was finalized in light of the precious suggestions given by the said experts.

To check the reliability of the research tool, the researcher personally went to every respondent and administered the questionnaire among sixty (60) respondents, for assessing the reliability of the study, Chronbac alpha formula was used. Items whose total item correlation was found .25 or less than it dropped. Eleven items were dropped and the remaining retained thirty items were left with Cronbach alpha .893.

Results Discussion

The below table 3 shows that there is a significant relationship between the students’ academic achievement and AV Aids at Secondary School Level in Southern Districts of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan

Table 3. Linear Regression model shows the impact of AV Aids

Dependent Variable	R	R ²	DF	F	P	Beta	Sig
Academic achievement	.133	.018	1	8.979	.003 ^a	.133	.000
Respondent Students			498				
Independent Variable							
Av aids							

Table 3 shows the impact of AV aids materials on students' academic achievement at Secondary School level. R square is found .018 while the multiple R is .133^a which expresses the relationship between dependent and independent variables i-e Academic achievement of students and Av aid respectively. The F value has been also found significant which 8.979 at .000 the level of significance. The beta score was Significant at .003^a level of sig. All of the above statistical calculation revealed that there significant relationship between Audio-Visual aids and Students academic achievement at Secondary School Level

Table 4. Shows responses about the impact of A.V aids the academic achievement of students at secondary school level in southern districts of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa

Respondents		Yes	No	Total
Students	Frequency	355	145	500
	Percentage	70	30	100
Teachers	Frequency	139	61	200
	Percentage	68	32	100

Table 4 indicated the respondents' views regarding the "Impact of audiovisual aids on Students' academic achievement at Secondary School Level. It shows that the total numbers of the respondents were five hundred (500). It indicates that the total number of the respondents were 500, out of which 250 were female and 250 were a male student. 76% (386) respondents' views show "Yes" while the rest 24% (114) respondents' views show "No" responses regarding the impact of AV aids on students' academic achievement at Secondary School level.

Conclusion

It was concluded from the above all tables' results that the views of both the respondents i-e male and female indicated that the use of AV Aids or instructional supplies has a significant impact on secondary schools students' academic achievement. In the same way, the analysis and result of table No.3 also show that there is a significance relationship between the student academic achievement and audio-visual aids at secondary School level in Southern districts of KP, Pakistan.

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